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Hybridization of full-wave FDTD solver with a Multilevel Multiconductor Transmission Line solver with ngspice Interconnections

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1. Motivation

Image sourced from: <https://www.ashevillemica.com>

Sourced from Oskay and Schlaepfer. Open Circuits, The Inner Beauty of Electronic Components. Ed. No Starch Press. 2023.

1. Introduction to FDTD

- In FDTD, discretizing the space results in rectangular geometries.
- The smaller the spatial step, the longer the simulation runtime.

2. Dynamics of the system

Consider a shielded MTL with m levels and n_c conductors inside a field domain. The interaction between the fields and the TL is described by the following set of equations

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \times \mathbf{E} &= -\mu \frac{\partial \mathbf{H}}{\partial t} \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{H} &= \varepsilon \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} + \sigma \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{J}_s \end{aligned} \quad \leftarrow \text{Maxwell's equations}$$

Coupling

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_z \{\mathbf{V}\} &= -[\mathbf{L}] \partial_t \{\mathbf{I}\} - [\mathbf{R}] \{\mathbf{I}\} + [\mathbf{Z}] * \{\mathbf{I}\} + \{\mathbf{E}_T\} \\ \partial_z \{\mathbf{I}\} &= -[\mathbf{C}] \partial_t \{\mathbf{V}\} - [\mathbf{G}] \{\mathbf{V}\} + [\mathbf{Y}] * \{\mathbf{V}\} \end{aligned} \quad \leftarrow \text{Telegrapher's equations}$$

With $\{\mathbf{V}\}(z, t) = [V_1^1, V_2^2 \dots V_{n_j}^2 \dots V_{n_k}^m \dots V_{n_c}^m]^T$ and $\{\mathbf{I}\}(z, t) = [I_1^1, I_2^2 \dots I_{n_j}^2 \dots I_{n_k}^m \dots I_{n_c}^m]^T$, where V_j^i correspond to the voltage of the j -th conductor (belonging to the i -th level) and I_j^i the current in that conductor.

2. Discretization

$$\mathbf{H}^{n+1/2} = \mathbf{H}^{n-1/2} - \frac{\delta t}{\mu} \nabla \times \mathbf{E}^{n+1}$$

$$\mathbf{E}^{n+1} = \frac{\varepsilon - \sigma \Delta t / 2}{\varepsilon + \sigma \Delta t / 2} \mathbf{E}^n + \frac{\Delta t}{\varepsilon + \sigma \Delta t / 2} \left(\nabla \times \mathbf{H}^{n-1/2} - \mathbf{J}_s^{n-1/2} \right)$$

$$\{\mathbf{V}\}_k^{n+1} = F_{V+}^{-1} [F_{V-} \{\mathbf{V}\}_k^n - (\{\mathbf{I}\}_k^{n-1/2} - \{\mathbf{I}\}_{k-1}^{n-1/2})]$$

$$\{\mathbf{I}\}_k^{n+1/2} = F_{I+}^{-1} \left[F_{I-} \{\mathbf{I}\}_k^{n-1/2} - (\{\mathbf{V}\}_{k+1}^{n+1} - \{\mathbf{V}\}_k^{n+1}) + \mathbf{E}_T - \Delta z \sum_i [q_3]_i [\varphi]_i^{n-1} \right]$$

Where:

$$F_{V\pm} = \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} [\mathbf{C}] \pm \frac{\Delta z}{2} [\mathbf{G}] \right)$$

$$F_{I+} = \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} [\mathbf{L}] + \frac{\Delta z}{2} [\mathbf{R}] + \frac{\Delta z}{2} [\mathbf{d}] + \frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} [\mathbf{e}] + \Delta z \sum_i [q_1]_i \right)$$

$$F_{I-} = \left(\frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} [\mathbf{L}] - \frac{\Delta z}{2} [\mathbf{R}] - \frac{\Delta z}{2} [\mathbf{d}] + \frac{\Delta z}{\Delta t} [\mathbf{e}] - \Delta z \sum_i [q_2]_i \right)$$

What happens if we have unshielded cables?

2. Unshielded cables

- Dynamics described using currents and p.u.l. charges on each wire.
- In-cell parameters instead of p.u.l. parameters.

2. Terminations

Hybridization of Multiconductor Transmission Line Solver With Circuit Solver Ngspice to Treat Line Interconnections and Terminations

Alberto Gascón Bravo , *Senior Member, IEEE*

- The terminal conditions are not collocated neither in space or time.
- We use the circuit solver ngspice to treat the terminations of the MTLs.

3. Experimental validation. Shielded and unshielded

3. Experimental validation. Shielded and unshielded

3. Experimental validation. Terminations

3. Experimental validation. Terminations

How can you use this
method?

4. Code implementation

OpenSEMBA

README.md

OpenSEMBA is an open-source repository of codes for solving electromagnetic problems. It includes solvers based on FDTD, DGTD, MTLN, FEM and generate meshes. This repository is mainly developed and maintained by the [Group of Electromagnetism of Granada \(GEG\)](#) from the [University of Granada \(UGR\)](#). Some of these solvers are included in the [Elemwave](#) suite which provides a user-friendly interface.

Contact us at Imdiazangulo@ugr.es

Pinned

fdtd Public

semba-fdtd is a finite-differences in time domain solver with special focus on EMC problems. semba-fdtd can be used as a standalone solver or integrated within a FreeCAD workbench (www.elemwave.com).

● Fortran ☆ 22 🍴 7

dgtd Public

Maxwell's curl equations solver using discontinuous Galerkin methods.

● C++ ☆ 24 🍴 3

tessellator Public

Tessellator is a mesher focused on generate meshes and data structures which are suitable for FDTD algorithms.

● C++ ☆ 7 🍴 6

tulip Public

Tulip is a per unit length multiconductor transmission line and in-cell parameters solver

● C++ ☆ 2 🍴 2

- Collaborative repository on GitHub.
- Open source and free to use.
- You are welcome to contribute or request improvements!!

People

ELEM WAVE

Combo View

Model Tasks

- Unnamed1
 - Simulation
 - Analysis
 - Model
 - Layer
 - PEC
 - uav
 - Probes
 - Far field
 - Domain
 - Sources
 - Grid
 - Boundaries

Property	Value
Base	
> Placement	[(0,00 0,00 1,00); 0,00 °; (0,00 mm 0...
Label	Boundaries

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Thank you for your attention

Any questions?

ELEM WAVE

